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A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF INTERACTION BETWEEN HUMANS AND NETWORKED PRODUCTS

A CASE STUDY OF BLUETOOTH NETWORKED PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

An increasing number of products are connected via networks becoming a system of two or more devices. In this situation, a user needs to control the connection and termination of the devices as well as the functional usage of each device. Designing interaction for such a complex system becomes a challenging problem in mediating its system model and users' mental model. In this paper we present gaps between the system model and users' conceptual models of the interaction of Bluetooth networked devices, and discuss interface design problems. The main differences of the two models from an observational study are as follows: First, users' interaction on a current device case has simplified steps and information compared to the system requirements. Second, a number of connections can be tangled in a user interaction. Third, device identification becomes a serious problem on multi- device network.

Keywords: conceptual model, networked devices, Bluetooth

INTRODUCTION

More and more products are being used in networks of two or more devices. An MP3 player is connected and used together with a Bluetooth headset. A car stereo system is connected to a cellphone. Although the connection between products provides various functional benefits, such conveniences cannot always be readily enjoyed owing to difficulties that users face when trying to operate the devices together. One of the interaction problems is to control the connection and termination of each device as well as the interaction issues between devices. Most current

solutions have focused on interaction around single devices. People's interactions with multiple networked devices are not fully understood. Because the system is not considered inter-related and tends to be developed separately, users' conceptual models may not match well with that of the networked devices system, thereby causing difficulties in use.

In this paper, we examine the human and multi-devices interaction. In particular we focus on interaction issues caused when Bluetooth networked devices are used for pre-connection, connection, and then termination. As a preliminary study to examine the system model and user model, the Bluetooth technology requirements and specifications in each connection stage were compared with actual users' interaction and problems. A user study was conducted to understand interaction problems. We aimed at identifying the gaps between a system model and a user model and interface design issues and solutions to mediate them. This can help designers create more understandable interfaces for interrelated network systems.

INTERACTION OF NETWORKED DEVICES

Norman (1988) explained that a good system helps to establish an appropriate conceptual model for users. The user's mental model is developed through interaction with the system. The system image is the visible part of the device that users interact with, like system interface. A user forms his/her conceptual model and can control the function through the system image of the device. A system model, which is the term we newly defined and added to the conceptual models, contains visible and

invisible parts of the device's operation including system requirements and activity specifications for proper functioning of the system, which are carried out through user interaction or without the user's involvement.

Norman's explanation about the conceptual models focuses on interaction between a person and a single device, which is most common in HCI researches (see Figure 1). A user forms a conceptual model and controls the function through interaction with a system image of a single device.

Figure 1. User-single device system interaction

Figure 2 shows a user-system interaction where a person interacts with two devices, such as an Mp3 player and a Bluetooth earphone. In this interaction, a user needs to manage not only each device's functions but also the identification and connection of the two devices via system images of the two devices. The system model and user's conceptual model become significantly complex, because the models include the connection of the network as well as control of the functions of each device.

Figure 2. User - Networked system interaction

As the system model and user model become complex, designing a system image that mediates

them becomes a much more complex design problem. To provide a system interface to adjust them appropriately, a designer needs to understand the gap between the user's model and the system model. In this study, we analyzed the system model of the Bluetooth connection and the user model shown in the user interaction.

THE SYSTEM MODEL OF BLUETOOTH CONNECTION

In order to analyze the system model consisting of technology specifications and requirements, which originate from the engineer's conceptual model, we conducted two interviews with an engineer who is an expert of Bluetooth technology and has developed Bluetooth devices. Through these interviews along with references from Nokia (2003), Palm (2005), Rathis (2000), and Liu (n.d.), we could understand Bluetooth technology requirements and formal specifications for Bluetooth technology. Figure 3 illustrates the common interconnection structure and technological requirements of a Bluetooth network connection. It summarizes user-related requirements and interconnection procedures rather than Bluetooth hardware specifications or signal transmission packets.

The connection includes the stages of pre-connection, connection, maintaining the connection, and disconnection. When two Bluetooth devices are connected by a communication channel, the connection between the two devices goes through multiple steps: Physical, Data, Application, and Function. In order to have a successful physical link, each of the two devices should be in an appropriate status, either turned on or allowing exchange of communication signals in the pre-connection stage. Connection starts with pairing and PIN code authentication. Pairing happens when two Bluetooth enabled devices agree to communicate with one another. A PIN code-- an ASCII string up to 16 characters in length-- is used for authentication between the two Bluetooth devices. In the service application link, profiles are specifications that define the Bluetooth services, such as hands-free, stereo headset, file transfer, and so on. During the ensuing interaction after their connection is set up, the two devices change their connection

Figure 3. System model of Bluetooth connection. Time flows from left to right along the x-axis, and the devices are shown along the y-axis. The interconnection requirements are given as text along the y-axis between the devices, and the stages of the interaction are shown as text along the x-axis.

status among a variety of states: hold, park, or sniff, and return to an active state depending on their frequency of functional activities. Finally, the connection is ended either by automatic completion of the desired functions, deliberate action by the user, or by an error at any time during the interaction.

Many factors affect the connection of the devices at different levels, such as the physical distance between the devices, device compatibility, profile compatibility, and even such seemingly straightforward issues as whether the devices are turned on and working normally. In addition, some of the devices may already be involved in a network connection that might prohibit additional interconnections due to the network structure.

OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO UNDERSTAND USER MODELS

Figure 3 shows a conceptual model of a Bluetooth connection based on technological specifications and references and my own understanding of the technological requirements. This model is reasonably accurate. The everyday user will not have such a detailed technological model. Users construct their own conceptual models in their heads: a user's model (Norman, 1988). Although it is not possible to directly analyze the user's conceptual model, we can infer the model by understanding the user's

interactions with a system. Five novice users were observed while they connected three Bluetooth devices, an Mp3 player (Samsung Yepp R1), a Bluetooth earphone (TSW-MH-806), and a Bluetooth speaker (Motorola EQ5), (see Figures 4 and 5). The purpose of this observational study is to see users' actual interactions with Bluetooth devices, when and what problems users face and how users' thoughts are different from the system model at moments where they experience difficulties, and how the differences are related to the system interface by which users perceive and understand the system.

Figure 4. Samsung Yepp R1 Mp3 player. Left: Graphical Interface of main screen, Right: graphical interface of Bluetooth connection screen.

Figure 5. Devices used in the study. Left: A Bluetooth speaker, Motorola EQ5, Right: a Bluetooth earphone, TSW-MH-806

Because people often are frustrated with Bluetooth technology, the participants were recruited from among university undergraduate and graduate students in their 20s who feel relatively comfortable with handling new technologies compared to other groups. In the study, experienced users were excluded because their conceptual model is formed not only from their perceptions and understanding of the system image but also from training and instructions in previous Bluetooth usage. Because all the participants are Korean, all the devices used in the study were purchased in Korea and the main language of the Mp3 player interface was Korean. All observations were conducted in the same room where a desk, a chair, and a video camera were set up. A very short introduction of what the devices were and how to turn them on was provided to the participants before they started the tasks, but the instructions did not include explanations about graphical and physical interfaces for Bluetooth connection. The participants were asked to perform the tasks without instructions and without providing a manual of the interface in order to eliminate influential information other than system images.

Figure 6. Video recorded user activities.

In the first task, the participants were asked to select either a speaker or an earphone and connect it to the Mp3 player. The first task is aimed to reveal how users' concepts have been changed until they successfully connect two devices and how their intermediate trials are different from the

technological system model. Three participants started with the TSW-MH-806 earphone in the first task, and two participants started with the Motorola EQ5 speaker. In the second task performed after a participant successfully performs the first task, the participant is asked to connect to the other device that he or she did not select in the first task. The third task is to reconnect the device that the participant had connected to in the first task. The second task is intended to show the interaction when a previous connection is replaced with a new connection or the two connections occur together. The third task is to make reconnection of the devices. All user activities were video recorded and analyzed after they were transcribed into text. Figure 6 shows examples of the recorded user activities.

FINDINGS FROM THE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

The observed users' interactions and problems in each network connection stage from the three tasks were as follows:

STANDBY AND PRE-CONNECTION STAGE

The earphone and the speaker used in the study have different interfaces in the pre-connection stage: The earphone needs to be set up to an inquire and page status to establish a new connection by pushing a physical button long enough until the red and blue lights blink. The Motorola speaker does not have that status to be set up and it can be searched from other devices if the speaker is turned on.

In the pre-connection stage, all the participants started with turning on the two devices to be connected. After the standby stage, two among three participants who connected the earphone had difficulties setting up the inquire-page status of the earphone. In contrast, the other three participants did not need to set it up because the speaker automatically started the inquire-page without user interaction or the earphone automatically connected to the Mp3 player, because it was in a reconnection procedure due to the influence of the prior connection. After a few trials in which one participant had difficulty starting the inquire-page status of the earphone, she asked, "What button turns on the Bluetooth?" Although the earphone was

in the Bluetooth usage status, she thought that the Bluetooth was not working.

Another problem revealed in the study was device identification. The Mp3 player interface displays connection with Bluetooth devices in two ways: a device is represented by a device code, such as 0018E4227C5D, and the device code is changed to its model number, such as TSW-MH-806, after Mp3 player receives information about the connecting devices. While the interface shows devices with codes or a model numbers, three participants were confused over matching the codes to the following model numbers or in matching the model numbers to the real devices. One participant was confused over matching the devices and model number, and she tried to control the wrong device for a period of time. This happened frequently in the second or third tasks when the participants were asked to identify the previously connected device and a new device.

CONNECTION STAGE

In the system model, the actual connection starts in the connection stage after devices identify each other in the pre-connection stage. The connection stage is the main procedure of the connection where actual interconnection occurs. In this stage, the connection is established if several layers are successfully interconnected: physical, data, application, and function layers. Differently with the system model consisting of complex interconnection procedure, the majority of participants (four of five) indicated that they are expecting a completed connection when they found that a device is identified on a Mp3 player. Participants checked the sound of the device immediately after the Mp3 player identified the earphone or the speaker. Two participants even expected automatic and prompt connection right after they turned on the devices. From their behavior, it could be inferred that participants have a model of a very simple connection stage that is completed if devices are identified and that is far from the actual connection stage of the system model consisting of several layers.

The graphic interface of Samsung Yepp R1, the Mp3 player used in the study, shown in the right picture

of Figure 4, may add problems on user understanding. It shows devices on a screen if they are identified. If a user touches the icon representing the identified device, the icon glows. Two participants in the study were confused by the feature that the Bluetooth connection of the device is established if the device icon is glowing, but the glowed icon does not represent any actual change on the system. The connection stage is started if a user drags the icon onto the central icon. Three participants among five had difficulties in figuring out how to trigger the connection stage.

When the actual interconnection starts, participants were asked a yes or no question, "Do you want pairing?" and/or were asked to enter a "PIN code" on a text box. None of the five participants knew what the pairing or PIN code meant and how they should react to the message or the box. Another case where the user's choice is queried in the connection stage is about profiles. When the participants got to the screen for profile selection-- hands free, stereo headset, or file transfer-- they chose to return to the prior screen without making any choice, or they tried each of the profiles one by one and checked whether the connection worked in each selection. They may have thought that the profile choice was not related to the Bluetooth connection they desired or they may not have understood what each profile choice meant or which one to select.

Another interesting observation was that participants checked the connection very frequently. When the participants used the earphone, they checked the sound, which is a signal of successful connection, after every activity. After checking the earphone for sound a few times, two participants decided to wear the earphone continuously to check the connection even though they could not hear any music. This showed the importance of continuous feedback with which a user obtains information regarding how the connection is proceeding or if it has succeeded or failed.

One more problem we found was interruption from other connections. Theoretically, a Bluetooth device allows concurrent connections with 7 different devices. However, a prior connection can disturb

another device's connection because of technological problems on signals, network structure, or application purpose. For instance, two devices cannot share a Bluetooth headset to play music at the same time. In the observation, participants attempted to disconnect all previously connected devices to ensure that the new connection was not interrupted. However, in the case where participants disconnected or removed a device only from the Mp3 player interface and did not turn off the device, the device automatically reconnected and disturbed the new connection when the user searched for the new device. In another case where a participant only turned off the device and did not remove it from the interface, the icon remained on the screen, leading to confusion regarding device identification.

MAINTAINING CONNECTION STAGE

This study was not appropriate to observe the maintaining connection stage. This stage can be observed when a user uses Bluetooth devices for a certain length of time with changes in the purpose or state of usage, but user observation was conducted in this study by asking participants to perform certain tasks in a relatively short time. User interaction in this stage should be studied more seriously in future study.

RECONNECTION STAGE

Originally we intended to observe the reconnection stage in the third task, in which the participants reconnect to the device that they had connected to in the first task. However, the influence of the reconnection of the devices was also observed in the first and the second tasks while participants were handling the devices.

The reconnection stage reduced the difficulties in the original connection stage substantially and provided convenience in cases where there was no unexpected trouble. Three among four participants completed the third task in very short time. One participant did not perform the reconnection stage and repeated the whole procedure of the pre-connection and connection stages in the third task because she had entirely removed the connection in the second task. Another participant successfully connected in the first task very simply because the

devices were already in the reconnection stage due to influence from the previous participant's study. However, if the reconnection was interrupted for any reason, the limited information from the reconnection stage could not provide help to users to establish reconnection. In the case of one participant who had trouble reconnecting the device, she received a message "the connection has failed" without any further guidance.

EXPERIMENTAL ISSUES

Because we wanted to observe broad user activities, problems, and system images that users interact within a natural environment, it was difficult to control the tasks and devices. The two devices that participants selected in their first task, the earphone (TSW-MH-806) and a Bluetooth speaker (Motorola EQ5), had different interfaces to set up the inquire-page status. Because of this, we could compare the pros and cons of each interface related to user Bluetooth interaction, but the data of the two groups could not be compared directly.

In addition, because of a variety of technical issues, we were unable to control the similarities among the devices and the ability to do a full reset and "clean boot" after each experimental run which made it difficult to control the influence from previous connections. Each succeeding participant used the same devices that a previous participant had used. We removed all connections and device information from the MP3 player and turned the power off for all three devices before the devices were provided to the next participant. However, in one participant's case, we discovered that the connection had started at the reconnection stage. With the R1 MP3 player interface, it was difficult to confirm that all the previous information was deleted and to maintain the same task conditions.

Although these technical problems made it difficult to do a precise comparison of the situations, we believe that the qualitative results were only minimally affected. If anything, the lack of a clean resetting of the devices should have made the task easier for participants later in the experiment, so the list of difficulties we observed would only have been larger had we been able to do a clean resetting

of the equipment. In future experiments, we will make sure we can do this.

COMPARISON DIAGRAM OF THE SYSTEM MODEL AND USER MODEL

User interaction and system interface observed from the user study can help us to infer a user model. We

diagrammed a possible user interaction of Bluetooth devices as presented in Figure 7b based on the findings from the observations and interfaces of the devices used in the user study. In Figure 7b, an Mp3 (Device A) player can be interconnected with several devices, such as earphones, a speaker, and another device (Device B, C, and D), at the same time but

Figure 7. Comparison of system model (a), user interaction (b), and system interface (c) of a Bluetooth connection case. Time flows from left to right along the x-axis, the devices are shown along the y-axis in each model. The interconnection requirements and problems are given as text along the y-axis between the devices, and the stages of the interaction are shown as text along the x-axis.

with different connection stages. The problems that novice users may experience in the interaction, which were observed from the user study, are given in small gray boxes along the related connection stages with text.

A user mainly interacts with the display interface of the Mp3 player among the devices. Figure 7c shows the activities and problems on the Mp3 player interface; they comprise the system image that a user would perceive during the system operation and forms user model on it.

GAPS BETWEEN THE SYSTEM MODEL AND USER MODEL

Comparison of the system model (7a), user interaction (7b), and system interface (7c) helped to identify gaps between the system model and user interaction and also revealed design issues. First, users' interaction has simplified steps and information compared to the system model. The simplified interfaces have pros and cons. Second, a number of connections can be tangled on a device. Third, device identification becomes a serious problem on user interaction.

SIMPLIFIED USER MODEL

Compared to the complex procedure and many requirements in each connection stage of the system model of 7a, user interaction and interface of 7b and 7c have relatively simplified models in some parts. Comparison of the system model and user interaction revealed the pros and cons of the simplified system images.

The simplified models may help users to perform interaction easily. In the pre-connection stage of Device C (a speaker), shown in 7b, the reduced user interaction requirement and steps of inquire-page helps users to easily connect the network. In the user study, all the participants more easily succeeded in establishing the speaker connection than the earphone connection. For the latter, the participants had difficulties finding how to move to the inquire-page status.

However, the simplified interface may form a gap between a system model and user's conceptual model in some cases which cause users' difficulty in system usage. Too much simplified interface does

not provide proper information and a conceptual model, when there is a problem and the connection fails. While a connection is not established if any of the several layers fails to interconnect in the connection stage, owing to one of several reasons such as technology compatibility, network structure, or application problems, the interface only shows a short message: 'The connection has failed.' The simplified message does not provide useful information regarding what caused the problem and what the user can do to fix the interconnection problems. This appears to be one of the most frustrating problems that participants faced in Bluetooth usage.

Also, the current graphical user interface of the Samsung Yepp Mp3 player does not help users to understand that there is a separate stage for connection establishment after devices are identified. The simple icon interface leads to a user model that breaks down with complex procedure of Bluetooth system model. Participants expected that the connection would be formed without additional action if the two devices identified each other.

On the other hand, users don't understand some technological terminologies and concepts with their conceptual model if they are not appropriately explained. Some terminologies in current Bluetooth interface, such as pairing, PIN code, or profiles were rooted from the system specifications and not modified in the system interface. None of the Korean novice participants of the study knew the meaning of "pairing" or "PIN number". Also, when participants viewed a message for selective profiles on an Mp3 player, they gave up selecting a profile or tried each of the profiles to check if the selection would establish the connection.

Therefore, a simplified interface model can help users to handle the connection conveniently. However, adjustments should be carefully considered to mediate the system model and the user interface at an appropriately simplified level so that users can handle the system with a proper conceptual model even when the connection fails. Also, a designer needs to moderate technological terminology into

friendly terms that users can easily understand from their conceptual model and prior experiences.

TANGLED CONNECTIONS

A big difference between the system model and user interaction was found in multi-device interaction. Generally, engineers and designers have focused on the connection between two devices, as in 7a, but we found that many connections with different devices can be tangled in actual user interaction. Each connection can be in different stages and the mixed stages of different connections (shown on one interface in Fig. 7c) confuse the user's conceptual model of connection status. Also, a connection between two devices is influenced by other devices' connections (Fig. 7b). A connection can fail because it is interrupted by other connections, which were previously set up or automatically reconnected. A short message, "the connection has failed," shown in the current interface, was not helpful for users to understand the possible influence of other connections.

DEVICE IDENTIFICATION PROBLEM

A more serious problem found in this analysis is identification of a device among many devices sharing an interface. Figure 7c shows the Mp3 player interface shared by many connections to provide information and feedback. Device identification was found to be an important issue at the pre-connection stage in the system model (Fig. 7a). However, in the actual user interaction (Fig. 7b) and its interface image (Fig. 7c), users can be confused over which device a message or action is related to among all of the stages. When a device is automatically reconnected but a user has not perceived the connection, the situation can be even more confusing. The identification problem is an important issue of Bluetooth networked interface design not only in the pre-connection stage but also for all feedback and actions of Bluetooth connection if more than two devices are connected. Also, there is a substantial difference between user-single device interaction and user-networked system interaction.

CONCLUSION

This study discussed interface design problems of networked devices through a comparison of a system model of Bluetooth technology connection and a user model identified from an observational study. The design suggestions based on the findings are as follows:

- The system interface design should be based on an appropriately simplified model. A simplified model at an appropriate level helps users to handle the system easily. A designer also needs to consider that the interface should help users' proper understanding when the connection is not properly established.
- A designer needs to moderate technological terminology into easy terms in a system interface that users can easily understand from their conceptual model and prior experiences.
- Connection of multiple Bluetooth devices can influence or interrupt each connection. The system interface should alert that connection problem can be caused from a number of sources beyond the two devices a user intends to connect.
- All messages or actions should be easily identified as to which device is related to the action or message. Device identification becomes a serious problem not only in the pre-connection stage but also for all feedback and actions of the Bluetooth connection if more than two devices are connected.

The purpose of this study is to determine a system model and typical users' conceptual models of the Bluetooth interaction. Although the discussion is limited in a few Bluetooth device interfaces and interactions, this study helps to define gaps between a system model and a user's conceptual model. The next step of future study will be to explore the gaps in real situations with a wide range of devices in order to obtain a deeper understanding of system models and user models. Design guidelines and examples based on profound understanding of networked systems will help designers and engineers to create understandable Bluetooth technology interface mediating system models and common user models.

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